

The application of adjectives, as well as issues and solutions around their usage

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Abstract:

This article is about the superlative adjectives, monosyllabic superlative adjectives, polysyllabic superlative adjectives, stem-changing adjectives. this article also discusses the words used with superlative adjectives and by far.

Key words: the superlative adjectives, monosyllabic superlative adjectives, polysyllabic superlative adjectives, stem-changing adjectives, signal words of adjectives and by far.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many international certifications also test writing skills. These skills require effective use of words to achieve superior results. In particular, the effective use of adjectives allows the learner to get a high score from the above skill. However, understanding the 3 types of degrees of quality is a bit of a problem. however, knowing how to build adjectives, correctly analyzing the signal words used with it, and working with words that enhance the meaning of the adjective can prevent such problems. Therefore, this article analyzes the necessary and interesting information for the learner about accretive adjectives, their formation, signal words of accretive adjectives, words that strengthen the meaning of the adjective, and by for.

II. MATERIALS

Usages. Superlative adjectives are used when comparing three or more people or things. We use article “the” before the superlative.

Making adjectives of the superlative degree from positive adjectives:

1) One-syllable adjectives. To form superlative adjectives from one-syllable positive adjectives, the suffix -est is added to the adjective.

For example:

- a) cheap-**the*** cheapest
- b) large-**the** largest
- c) big-**the** biggest

2) **-y adjectives.** Adjectives ending in -y are written with the suffix -iest to form accusative adjectives.

For example:

a) lazy-**the laziest**

b) easy-**the easiest**

3) **Adjectives with two or more syllables.** To make superlative adjectives from positive adjectives consisting of two or more syllables, the word most must be used before the adjective.

For example:

a) beautiful-the most beautiful

b) intelligent-the most intelligent

4) **Irregular adjectives.** A table of irregular adjectives is used to making the superlative adjectives from positive adjectives.

For example:

a. Good-the best

b. Old-the eldest/oldest

c. Far-the farthest

d. Bad-the worst

e. Well-the best

f. Little-the least

g. Many-the most

h. Late-the last/latest

List of making the superlative

No		Positive adjective	The superlative
1.	One-syllable adjectives	Cheap Large Big	Cheapest Largest Biggest
2.	-y adjectives	Easy Lazy	Easiest Laziest

3.	Adjectives with two or more syllables	Intelligent Beautiful	Most intelligent Most beautiful
4.	Irregular adjectives	Good Old Far Bad Well Little Many Late	Best Eldest/oldest Farthest Worst Best Least Most Last/latest

*article the is usage before the superlative

Signal words of the superlative

One of...;

of the three/ four....;

of all ;

of +noun (of the year, of my life,;)

in + where (in the world, in the city, in the class,;)

have/has ever;

I know;

.....can/could;

among;

The second/the third.....

Example :

- 1) Paris is one of the most beautiful citiest.
- 2) Of the three boys, Tom is the tallest.
- 3) Canada is the second largest country.
- 4) He is the happiest person I know.

By far. By far is used before an the superlative of adjective to strengthen the meaning.

By far + the superlative

Example : Jack is by far the cleverest student in the class.

I. RESULT AND CONCLUSION

Finally, we conclude that accusative adjectives play an important role in our speech. Because, the noun group that is actively used in our oral speech, in turn, requires the strengthening of the meaning and the effective increase of artistic coloring in our words. However, due to the presence of other levels of quality in the speech process: positive adjectives and comparative adjectives, the extensive use of accusative adjectives causes some inconvenience to the learner. and then, it is appropriate that they pay attention to the skill of making an incremental level of quality. Each quality level has its own characteristics, so students are advised to take into account the above points and rely on the points given for the quality level.

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